

IMPACT OF ABSENTEE PARENTS ON THE PSYCHO-SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND THE BEHAVIORAL CHANGES AMONG THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Parent is the one who gives birth to or nurtures and raises a child. Nowadays, numbers of parents that are far away from their children are continuously rising and this might have an impact to their children. Whether a parent's absence is short-lived or long-lived, the fact remains that it will affects positive or negative on their children's behavior. The effects of absent parents on their often leave him unable to make healthy relationships, or he may have stress related illnesses due to the unresolved conflicts of his childhood. And often if they don't, they will suffer from guilt even if the parent never admits their own failure to care for their child's behavior. So that, the school of the students will develop a program that will create involvement of parents for a student's well-being that will help them to succeed in life. To support, this research study is presenting impact of absentee parents on the psycho-socioeconomic status and the behavioral changes among the students. The survey questionnaire led in attaining the main objectives of the study partaking one hundred fifty (150) grade six students in this academic year 2020-2021. Based on the findings, the absentee parent factor and environment interaction are significantly related to psychological status, socioeconomic status and the behavioral changes of the students. The research study recommended that parents may create time management to have time with their own children to avoid of their absence. Nevertheless, the school of the children will develop a program that will create involvement of parents for a child's well-being that will help them to overcome stress caused of absentee parents. In line with this, they will be found out that communicating with children is needed to avoid absenteeism of parents that cause negative effects in their psychological status, socioeconomic status and behavioral changes.

Keywords: Absentee parent, Environment Interaction, Psychological status, Socioeconomic status, Behavioral changes